

THE MECHANISMS OF ELEVATED TEMPERATURE PROPERTY LOSSES

IN HIGH PERFORMANCE STRUCTURAL EPOXY RESIN MATRIX MATERIALS AFTER

EXPOSURES TO HIGH HUMIDITY ENVIRONMENTS

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Absorbed moisture was found to plasticize the type of cross-linked epoxy resin system investigated, causing a lowering of the T_g and in turn affecting mechanical response, such as by shifting the relaxation moduli to shorter times. The phenomenon is described and quantified in terms of an existing free volume theory relationship. Weight gains greater than equilibrium amounts were observed without accompanying T_g changes which is attributed to moisture entrapment during microcracking in the resin. Creep studies performed under water at 300°F (149°C) established an additional mechanism for loss of elevated temperature properties which is characterized by the appearance and growth of cracks in the material. The observed failure processes are described in terms of an existing theory for rupture of cross-linked rubbers. The process is governed by the synergistic effects of moisture, temperature, and stress. Moisture changes the viscoelastic response of the material so that stress-induced crack formation and growth is facilitated.

Introduction

Structural composite materials derived from epoxy resins and fibrous reinforcements such as glass, graphite, and boron filaments have found ever increasing importance in the field of commercial and military aircraft and space systems. This trend will undoubtedly continue with major interest concentrated on organic matrix composites reinforced with graphite and/or boron fibers. To derive the maximum benefit from these high performance reinforcements the organic resin matrices utilized must retain a high percentage of their initial physical properties over a wide range of temperature and humidity conditions. In the case of epoxy resins it has been shown (1-3) that their elevated temperature, 300-350°F (149-177°C), mechanical properties (tensile strength and modulus, flexural strength and modulus, etc.) are adversely affected as a result of moisture absorbed from high humidity environments. Similar elevated temperature property losses are observed (4) in composite properties which are matrix sensitive (transverse tension, compression, shear, etc.). This absorption of moisture in different temperature/humidity conditions and its subsequent diffusion has been described in several papers (4-7).

The mechanisms of these elevated temperature property losses in epoxy resin matrix materials resulting from moisture absorbed from high humidity

environmental exposures can be grouped into two general classifications: (1) losses due to moisture-induced plasticization, and (2) losses due to moisture-induced mechanical damage, namely resin micro-cracking or cracking. These two types of mechanisms will be addressed herein.

This investigation specifically considered an epoxy resin formulation that is characteristic of a variety of advanced composite and adhesive systems. It contains a multifunctional epoxy (tetraglycidylmethylene dianiline), a diamine curing agent (diaminodiphenylsulfone), and an organometallic catalyst (boron trifluoride monoethylamine). Test specimens (varying from films to thick plates) were prepared by casting the resin between pyrex glass plates using appropriate spacers. Maximum cure temperature of the castings was 350°F (177°C) for 60 minutes. All machined test specimens were examined with polarized lenses prior to testing to ensure that no residual stresses or cracks were present.

Moisture-Induced Plasticization

There are several factors which can affect the glass transition temperature, T_g , of a polymer, but the one of prime interest here is associated with changes arising from the absorption of water into the cured epoxy structure. It is an accepted theory (8) that at and below the T_g , 1/40 of the total volume of the material is free volume (total volume less molecular volume). If this is true, then the T_g can be altered by changing the polymer's free volume at a given temperature. If a polymer were mixed with a miscible liquid that contains more free volume than the pure polymer, then the T_g will be lowered. In particular, if it is further assumed that the free volumes are additive, then the polymer-diluent mixture will contain more free volume at a given temperature than would the polymer alone. As a result, plasticized polymers must be cooled to a lower temperature in order to reduce their free volume to 1/40 of the total volume of the polymer-diluent combination. This is the process which is proposed to occur when moisture is absorbed into an epoxy resin.

Based on the above assumptions, Bueche and Kelley (9) derived the following expression for the T_g of a plasticized system (polymer + diluent):

$$T_g = \frac{\alpha_p V_p T_{gp} + \alpha_d (1-V_p) T_{gd}}{\alpha_p V_p + \alpha_d (1-V_p)} \quad (1)$$

where,

- T_{gp} = T_g of the polymer
- T_{gd} = T_g of the diluent
- α_p = polymer expansion coefficient
- α_d = diluent expansion coefficient
- V_p = volume fraction of polymer

In terms of the percent weight gain in the polymer, M,

$$V_p = \frac{1}{1 + (\rho_p/\rho_d) [(0.01)M]} \quad (2)$$

where ρ_p and ρ_d are the densities of the polymer and diluent, respectively.

The technique which was selected for making T_g measurements was a beam bending test (three-point loading) performed in a heated oil bath. A stress of 264 psi (1.82 MPa) is applied to a specimen measuring 5.0 in. (12.7 cm) long by 0.5 in. (1.27 cm) thick by 0.125 in. (0.318 cm) wide. A constant heat-up rate of 2°C per minute is maintained. Measurements are made of temperature versus specimen deflection for various water weight gains (W.G.). The large size of the specimen and the presence of the oil bath were expected to minimize water loss during testing. This was confirmed by post-test measurements which yielded weight losses less than 10% of pretest water weight gain. Loss of water during T_g measurement is a major concern when studying a moisture-plasticized polymer having a T_g greater than the boiling point of water. This is particularly significant for any technique that utilizes a small sample having a large surface area-to-weight ratio. The particular test utilized herein relied on large specimens so that water loss during testing was minimized.

T_g values determined from various individual temperature-deflection curves were plotted as a function of weight percent water content for absorptions at 100% R.H. and 75% R.H. (Fig. 1). There is a gradual lowering of T_g until the equilibrium moisture content associated with the particular humidity condition is reached, whereupon there is no further lowering of the T_g . This observation is evidence to support the contention that micro-cracking is responsible for weight gains greater than equilibrium values (see next section). If the additional water were being physically absorbed there would have been a further decrease in T_g .

It should be noted that when measurements are being made of T_g vs. water weight gains, nonuniform moisture distributions will be present in the specimens until an equilibrium moisture content is achieved. These non-uniformities would influence the experimental results in a manner dependent on the particular experimental technique being employed. Therefore, to meaningfully apply a quantitative relationship such as Equation (1), it is important to have a uniform, equilibrium distribution of moisture in the test specimens.

The T_g values for equilibrium moisture contents were combined to produce a plot of T_g versus equilibrium weight percent water (Fig. 2). As noted, when the condition of equilibrium distribution of diluent is achieved, one can apply Equation (1) to arrive at a theoretical prediction of the effect of absorbed moisture on the T_g of the polymer. The theoretical curve, shown in Fig. 2 for comparison with the experimental data points, was derived from the following parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_p &= 3.78 \times 10^{-4}/^{\circ}\text{C} & \rho_p &= 1.28 \text{ g/cm}^3 & T_{gd} &= 4^{\circ}\text{C} \\ \alpha_d &= 4 \times 10^{-3}/^{\circ}\text{C} & \rho_d &= 1.0 \text{ g/cm}^3 \end{aligned}$$

The values of α_p and ρ_p were experimentally determined. The value of α_d is an average value calculated from a table of volumetric expansion data for water. An approximate value of T_{gd} was determined from the experimental data as recommended by Bueche (8). As shown in Fig. 2, the 75% R.H. and 100% R.H. data points for the effect of equilibrium moisture absorption on T_g are in accord with the Bueche-Kelley relationship.

To further illustrate the plasticization phenomenon, stress relaxation curves were prepared from constant strain rate tensile tests. Fig. 3 shows the typical relaxation behavior at various temperatures for the dry polymer specimens and for wet (equilibrium weight gain at 100% R.H./160°F) specimens. Using linear superpositioning (8), stress relaxation master curves were prepared for both wet and dry tests as shown in Fig. 4. The dramatic plasti-

Fig. 1 - T_g as a function of absorbed moisture for exposure conditions shown.

Fig. 2 - T_g vs. equilibrium weight gain.

Fig. 3 - Relaxation modulus as a function of temperature for dry control and wet (equilibrium weight gain at 100% R.H./160°F (71°C)) specimens.

Fig. 4 - Relaxation modulus master curves, reference temperature = 300°F (149°C).

cization effect of water is clearly evident. The presence of the plasticizer has shifted the curves to smaller times.

In a manner similar to calculating a temperature shift factor according to the WLF Equation (10), a shift factor for the displacement of the modulus curves to lower times due to plasticization by water was determined from the master curves in Fig. 4. A value of 10 was thus determined, which means that the same response will be exhibited 10 times faster by the "wet" specimen than the "dry" specimen.

The results of this plasticization investigation indicate that among its possible deleterious effects, water behaves as a classical plasticizer; i.e., it lowers the T_g of the epoxy as a function of the amount absorbed. This phenomenon also manifests itself in other concurrent effects such as swelling (see later section) and shifting the relaxation moduli curves to lower temperatures or, equivalently, to shorter times since the polymer is visco-elastic. These plasticization induced property losses can be translated into composite property losses for those properties that are matrix dominated or controlled.

Moisture-Induced Mechanical Damage

In a real-world environment that an aircraft sees, these materials will be subjected to varying environmental excursions - temperature in particular - instead of some constant temperature/humidity condition. To simulate this, specimens were subjected to the simulated real-life environmental exposure cycle shown in Fig. 5 (5). The rapid temperature rise to 300°F (149°C) followed by rapid cooling to ambient is referred to as a thermal spike.

In the course of this investigation, specimens were subjected to all phases of the cycle. The results of exposures to these conditions (rain/humidity/thermal spike/cold; rain/humidity/thermal spike; humidity only) are shown in Fig. 6. It is apparent that the thermal spike has increased both the rate and amount of moisture absorbed when compared to the conventional humidity only exposure.

Fig. 7 shows weight-gain vs. time plots for three different castings with all specimens being exposed to 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H. and one thermal-spike daily. Once the weight-gains exceed M_∞ the data become quite irregular with time as can be observed in Fig. 7. Also shown is weight-gain data for 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H. exposures only (no thermal-spikes), where for the long term data points some "scatter" is apparent when M_∞ (5.6%) is exceeded.

In order to examine the mechanism by which the thermal spike affects the weight gain process, specimens were subjected to the following exposures:

- I. 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H.
- II. 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H./1 Daily Thermal Spike
- III. 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H./4 Daily Thermal Spikes

The results of these exposures are illustrated in Fig. 8. It is apparent that the weight gains are proportional to the number of thermal-spikes experienced by the specimens and that the thermal-spike is the single most important factor in this environment causing increased moisture pickup. This type of behavior where irregular weight gains are observed when the weight gains (M_1) exceed M_∞ , can be attributed to micro-cracking in the specimens with water becoming entrapped in micro-cracks. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed on specimens which had been given exposures I, II, and III, with resultant weight gains of 5.6%, 6.7% and 7.4%, respectively. The SEM photo-

Fig. 5 - A simulated real-life environmental exposure cycle with a thermal spike to 300°F (149°C).

Fig. 6 - Epoxy moisture absorption as a function of simulated real-life exposure conditions.

Fig. 7 - Moisture absorption behavior of several epoxy castings (100% R.H./160°F (71°C)).

Fig. 8 - The effect of thermal spikes on epoxy moisture absorption (100% R.H./160°F (71°C)).

graphs of these specimens are shown in Fig. 9.

No cracks were observed after exposure I. However, some material is being compressed or forced out of the surface of the specimen by the swelling forces of the absorbed moisture. Specimens which had been given exposure II exhibited cracking around these compressed regions. Specimens which had been given exposure III exhibited the greatest amount of surface cracking, with the compressed material giving way completely to cracks.

Swelling

Another consequence of the moisture absorption process is that the specimen undergoes swelling to accommodate the water. Fig. 10 shows a plot of specimen thickness increase versus percent water absorbed. For the case of humidity-only exposures (160°F (71°C)/100% R.H.) the thickness increase is linear with absorbed moisture until M_{∞} (5.6%) is reached. Above M_{∞} the thickness increase is greater than linearity which is believed to be the consequence of crack formation.

Data are also shown in Fig. 10 for specimens which had received one daily thermal-spike in addition to constant temperature and humidity (160°F (71°C)/100% R.H.). In the weight-gain range of 1.5-2.0%, thermal-spiked specimens exhibit a substantially larger rate of thickness increase. These very large increases in thickness to levels significantly higher than those for humidity only, M_{∞} levels, are due to micro-cracking as previously discussed. To further illustrate, specimens which had increased in thickness by 4.5% at a weight gain of 8.4% were dried at 200°F under vacuum to constant weight. After drying, these specimens still had a residual thickness increase of 1.75%, which can be attributed to cracks and fissures in the specimen.

Environmentally Induced Stresses

The epoxy specimen's resistance to moisture induced swelling leads to the development of compressive stresses. In the diffusion process, a concentration gradient of moisture in the epoxy plate exists in the manner shown in Fig. 11 where M_0 and M_{∞} represent the initial (dry) and equilibrium moisture contents, respectively, and l is the thickness. The surface is at M_{∞} while the core is nearly dry early in the diffusion process. Therefore, compressive stresses ($-\sigma$) will be greatest at the surface. These will be balanced by biaxial tensile stresses ($+\sigma$) in the core of the material (11). For a constant temperature and humidity exposure the moisture gradient and corresponding stress state would have the appearance shown in Fig. 11. This condition will change with time as the interior moisture concentration approaches M_{∞} . Therefore, in the case of a constant humidity/temperature exposure there will be a stress field associated with the moisture gradient and this stress field will change as the moisture gradient changes.

For the case of the thermal-spike environment (Fig. 5), the moisture gradient will now be accompanied by a thermal gradient. Because of this, there will exist some net stress condition resulting from the linear superpositioning of the stresses for each type of gradient. For simplicity, it is assumed that each phenomenon is acting independently, that thermal diffusion is of greater magnitude than moisture diffusion, and the magnitudes of the moisture-induced and temperature-induced stresses are of the same order.

The different gradients, corresponding stress states, and net, combined stress states are shown in Fig. 11 for the thermal-spike/humidity environment. The specimen at room temperature in the humidity only condition has compressive stresses at the surface and tensile stresses in the core. A

I

II

III

Fig. 9 - SEM photographs of epoxy specimens after (I) exposure I (2000x), (II) exposure II (2000x), (III) exposure III (3000x).

Fig. 10 - Thickness increase as a function of moisture absorption.

thermal spike then produces a combined stress state, wherein the surface compressive stresses are reduced and the remaining stress field has the same profile, but is of different magnitude than the room temperature condition. Rapid cool down to room temperature results in a large tensile stress localized near the surface, balanced by a compressive stress through the center of the specimen. In essence, the humidity/thermal-spike environment causes the specimen to be cycled compression to tension.

No attempt is made here to place actual values on the stresses or to specify actual gradients. The purpose is to point out that gradients do exist (both moisture and thermal) and as a result corresponding stress states are imposed on the specimen. Whether or not micro-cracks could be formed and propagated as a result of these stresses will depend on both the magnitude of the stresses and number of times imposed.

Creep Studies

If a polymer is undergoing creep at a temperature above its T_g , an equilibrium elongation will be reached at the so called rubbery plateau. For a cross-linked system such as the epoxy resin or a rubber, no further elongation should be observed once the rubbery plateau is achieved because the load-bearing polymer chains between cross-links are fully extended. The continued elongation of a sample beyond its rubbery extension can only be due to chain scission processes. In addition, once the rubbery elongation is reached, in principle the specimen should be capable of remaining in that condition indefinitely if no chain scission is taking place. However, because of the formation and growth of micro-cracks, cavities, or other flaws or imperfections while in this stressed/elongated state, rupture takes place as a function of time, and therefore, time-to-rupture becomes a very meaningful parameter. Therefore, the creep test is capable of yielding considerable insight into the mechanisms of property loss.

A semi-quantitative theory describing the rupture of cross-linked rubbers has been provided by the work of Bueche and Halpin (12, 13). Their work assumes that the growth of cracks or flaws is controlled by the viscoelastic response of the material in the vicinity of the crack tip. In short, the rupture process is time-temperature dependent. Specifically, if a material is being tested above its T_g and the T_g were lowered by plasticization, the result would be a reduction in the rupture stress. Further, the lower the applied stress, the longer the time-to-break (t_b); and the higher the temperature, the lower the stress required for rupture; i.e., there is an equivalence of time and temperature on the rupture stress.

A further study (14) on cross-linked rubbers showed that in a suitable medium, cracks could be formed on the surface of specimens subjected to tensile stresses. These cracks grew perpendicular to the direction of the applied stress and their quantity increased with increasing stress or strain.

In relation to the creep test, the quantity of cracks formed should be proportional to the applied stress and, in turn, the greater the crack quantity the greater the probability of having cracks of sufficient size for crack growth to take place, thereby resulting in decreased time-to-break or lower rupture stresses. Alterations in the viscoelastic properties of the polymer (e.g., plasticization or changes in test temperature) should result in modifications of the time-to-rupture and crack growth process.

The creep tests performed in this study consisted of optically measuring the elongation as a function of time of an epoxy film specimen in a given environment under a constant load. To study the elevated temperature behavior of the epoxy as a function of moisture it is necessary to choose the

test conditions so that the cross-linked epoxy is in its rubbery state where the behavior of well-characterized, analogous systems such as the cross-linked rubbers can be used for reference. Another requirement is that the test temperature be lower than the cure (cross-linking reaction) temperature in order to avoid the complicating factor of additional cure. Further, it would be desirable that the test temperature be reasonably close to the use temperature of the material. All of these requirements are satisfied by the chosen test temperature of 300°F (149°C).

In the presence of moisture the effective T_g of the plasticized system is below 300°F (149°C) which satisfies the above requirement. However, since the boiling point of water is 212°F (100°C), it is necessary to perform the test in a pressure vessel. This ensures that steady-state conditions are present so that the results of the test are not diffusion-controlled. A pressure vessel was designed and built to achieve these test conditions. It consisted of a thick-wall pyrex glass tube specimen chamber (two feet high) and stainless-steel end caps having o-ring seals. Metal tie-rods were used to prevent the steam pressure from forcing off the end caps. One end cap was fitted with pressure fittings for evacuating the chamber and passing through inert gases. The use of the glass tubing allowed the strain measurements to be made optically.

The whole test set-up was mounted in a furnace for testing at 300°F (149°C). After adding double distilled water, the chamber was evacuated and then purged with nitrogen. The test was performed at 300°F (149°C) using a cathetometer to monitor movement of fiducial marks as a function of time. The ultimate stress, σ_u , used in guiding the tests, 1400 psi (9.66 MPa), was taken from the values found in constant strain rate tensile tests performed at 300°F (149°C) after equilibrium exposure at 160°F (71°C)/100% R.H.

Because of a slight temperature gradient from the bottom to the top of the test furnace, the upper part of the test chamber was at a slightly higher temperature than the 300°F (149°C) temperature maintained just below the surface of the water. Therefore, there was a lower moisture concentration at substantial distances above the water's surface than at and below the surface. This experimental condition was used as a means for testing specimens at two different moisture absorption contents. As previously discussed, the amount of moisture absorbed is directly proportional to the relative humidity or moisture concentration; therefore, performing the creep test underwater and substantially above the water would correspond to testing specimens of two different moisture contents. The underwater test was a "worst" condition that achieved maximum moisture content and is defined herein as saturation. The above water test achieved a lower moisture content, defined as less than saturation.

The results of the creep tests performed underwater at 300°F (149°C) are shown in Fig. 12 where percent elongation is plotted versus log time for stresses of 10, 20, 25, 30 and 50 percent of ultimate. With increasing stress there is a proportionate increase in elongation and decreased time-to-break. The shapes of the curves were quite similar to the creep curves and relaxation modulus curves previously presented. Within about 30 minutes all of the specimens had passed through the transition region and had reached the rubbery plateau. A plot of log stress and log elongation versus log time-to-break in the rubbery region yielded linear relationships for both stress and strain.

Polarized-light photomicrographs (20x) were taken after each creep test. Observations made from the photographs of the saturated, underwater exposed specimens are that the quantity of cracks is greater for the higher stress level specimens, the crack size increases with increased exposure time or time-to-break, and the cracks grow perpendicular to the direction of applied

Fig. 11 - Qualitative determination of gradients and stress states for thermal spike/humidity environment.

Fig. 12 - Elongation vs. time for creep tests at 300°F (149°C) and underwater (saturation).

stress. The photomicrograph of the 10% of ultimate specimen (Fig. 13) shows the unusual feature of micro-cracks growing across the width of the specimen in a manner that would lead to rupture. For comparison, polarized-light photomicrographs of an as-fabricated dry control specimen and a dry control specimen which had been subjected to a creep test in a dry nitrogen environment under a 50% of ultimate stress for one week showed no cracks. Elongation for the latter specimen was less than 0.7%.

Another series of 300°F (149°C) creep tests were performed in the pressure vessel at a height of eight inches above the water level. This was done to achieve another moisture concentration although it was impossible to experimentally measure it. The effect of this lower moisture concentration (< saturation) condition can be seen in Fig. 14 where percent elongation is plotted as a function of log time for stress levels of 10, 30 and 50 percent of ultimate. Compared with the underwater, saturation results (Fig. 12), the lower moisture concentration (< saturation) exposure yielded lower strains and increased exposure times at equivalent stress levels. Based on the results of the diffusion and T_g studies it is to be expected that lower moisture contents would result in less plasticization and, in turn, a smaller decrease in T_g .

Polarized-light photomicrographs were also taken for each of these tests. A gradual increase in crack density with increasing stress was evident, with the crack size increasing with exposure time. The dramatic effect of increased moisture concentration exposures could be observed by comparing underwater exposure photomicrographs with those of the lower moisture concentration (above water) exposure. For the 10% of ultimate stress level, comparison of the photomicrograph of the underwater exposure to that of the lower moisture concentration exposure (Fig. 13) shows the striking effect of moisture concentration on crack density and size. Both of these tests were for nearly equivalent exposure times with the saturated, underwater specimens (5-day exposure) rupturing and the above water, less than saturation specimens (6-day exposure) being removed without experiencing failure.

In another series of creep tests, specimens were tested underwater at 200°F (93°C). The elongation as a function of time for stresses of 10 and 30 percent of ultimate are shown in Fig. 14. Because of this lower temperature, decreased elongations and increased exposure times were observed relative to the 300°F (149°C) test for equivalent stress levels. In this case, the tests were terminated after five days exposure with no failures. Polarized-light photomicrographs, as well as the equivalent exposure times, showed that there was little observable difference at various stress levels at these test conditions. The dramatic effect of temperature can be seen by comparing the photomicrograph of the 300°F (149°C) test with that of the 200°F (93°C) test (Fig. 13) for the 10% of ultimate stress level.

Based on previous work with the analogous polymer systems of cross-linked rubbers, one mechanism by which moisture degrades the elevated temperature properties of the epoxy resin system can be postulated. Since there is no further elongation once the rubbery plateau is reached, chemical chain scission of any substantial magnitude can be eliminated (although very localized chemical chain scission in such areas as crack tips cannot be ruled out). Experimental results indicate that the failure processes can be described by the Bueche-Halpin theory for rupture of cross-linked rubbers. The times-to-rupture are proportional to the stress, plasticizer content, and test temperature; the quantity of cracks are time-temperature dependent. Thus, the rupture process (fracture-times and crack growth) are governed by the viscoelastic behavior of the material. This is clearly evident from the effect of different plasticizer content (i.e., different T_g 's) and temperature on the rupture behavior of the material.

Fig. 13 - Polarized-light photomicrographs (20x) of 10% of ultimate creep test specimens after 300°F (149°C) underwater (I), 300°F (149°C) above water (II), and 200°F (93°C) underwater (III) exposures.

Fig. 14 - Elongation vs. time for creep tests at 300°F (149°C) above water (< saturation) and 200°F (93°C) underwater (saturation).

Hence, in addition to moisture-induced plasticization, one significant mechanism for the loss of elevated temperature properties in a moisture environment is the formation and growth of cracks in the material. This process is governed by the combined effect of stress, temperature and moisture. Moisture changes the viscoelastic properties of the polymer so that stress-induced formation and growth of micro-cracks is facilitated. Further, it could be speculated that the crack growth process is aided by localized chemical chain scission at the crack tip.

Conclusions

The results of this work established the following:

- (1) Moisture concentration gradients will induce significant stress gradients within a cross-linked epoxy resin system.
- (2) Thermal spikes contribute to micro-cracking in the resin.
- (3) Weight-gains greater than equilibrium absorption levels are due to micro-cracking in the resin which results in an increase in moisture pick-up.
- (4) One mechanism for loss in elevated temperature properties is moisture-induced plasticization of the epoxy resin which causes a lowering of the T_g which in turn affects mechanical response such as by shifting the relaxation moduli to shorter times.
- (5) The lowering of a resin's T_g as a consequence of moisture plasticization can be explained in terms of free volume theory and can be quantified in terms of existing free volume theory relationships.
- (6) Creep studies showed that one mechanism for the loss of elevated temperature properties is the formation and growth of cracks. The failure process can be described by the Bueche-Halpin theory for rupture of cross-linked rubbers. The process is governed by the related effects of moisture, temperature, and stress. Moisture changes the viscoelastic response of the material so that stress-induced crack formation and growth is facilitated.
- (7) It can be inferred from the creep studies that no significant chemically induced chain scission is taking place; however, this does not completely rule out very localized chemical scission at such areas as the crack tips.

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